

Progressive Thoughts in Hem Barua's Select Poems: An Analytical Study

Ranjan Dutta¹
Dr. Maheswar Kalita²

¹Designation: Ph. D. Research Scholar, Department of Assamese, Cotton University
Guwahati, Assam, India e-mail: ranjandutta726@gmail.com

²Designation: Professor, Ph. D. Research Guide & HoD, Department of Assamese, Cotton
University, Guwahati, Assam, India, e-mail: maheswar.kalita@cottonuniversity.ac.in

Abstract :

Hem Barua (1915-1977) is one of the earliest poets of modern Assamese poetry. Hem Barua can be considered as one of the pioneering figures of modern poetry. In the past, the poems of a few modern poets expressed progressive thought, but for the first time in the history of Assamese Modern poetry Hem Barua is the poet whose poems deal with humanistic approach and optimism. , Hem Barua's poems is a realistic portrayal of issues related to society.

Key Words: Progressive Poems, humanism, classless society.

1.0 Introduction:

Hem Barua (1915-1977) is one of the earliest poets of modern Assamese poetry. Before Hem Barua, a couple of poets like Amulya Barua (1922-46), Chakreswar Bhattacharya (1918-69), Bhabananda Dutta (1918-59) and others started writing poetry for modern thought, but Hem Barua can be considered as one of the pioneering figures of modern poetry. He was more

disciplined than the earlier poets and his language was very lucid and fluent. The crisis of modern civilization, the degradation of human values are the issues which is being reflected in his poems; thereby contributing in the changing scenario of modern Assamese poems.

He sets a new trend in the poetry with his poem 'Bandar' published in 'Aabahan' in March 1940. He wrote poems in three magazines Jayanti (1943), Pasuwa (1948) and Ramdhenu (1951). Although, the seeds of progressive poems can be found in Jayanti Magazine, but it reached its fullness in the Ramdhenu Magazine. In this respect, the name of Hem Barua is praiseworthy.

Although it is found that the Progressive thoughts emerged in the forties in the history of Assamese poetry; but it cannot be considered as having artistic and humanistic approach. To be a truly progressive poet, one must love people. One of the poets whose name is worth mentionable in this regard is Hem Barua. Like other modern poets, Hem Barua's poetry was also influenced by the Marxist philosophy of class struggle. "He was elected to the Lok Sabha in the second general elections of 1957 as a member of the Socialist Party."¹ Perhaps because of his active involvement in socialism, in his literary works, most specifically in poems, Marxist philosophy is found. He was equally active in both politics and literature and had a realistic mind. In the past, the poems of a few modern poets expressed progressive thought, but for the first time in the history of Assamese Modern poetry Hem Barua is the poet whose poems deal with humanistic approach and optimism. Hem Barua was regarded as a role model by later modern poets and his poems still have relevance in today's literary world.

1.01 Scope of Topics:

This paper seeks to analyse how the progressive thoughts are being reflected in the book "Hem Baruar Kobita"

1.02 Research Methodology:

An analytical approach has been adopted in preparing the paper. The Primary source comprises of two collections of poetry by Hem Barua namely 'Hem Baruar Kobita' and

‘Adhunik Hahitya’ . On the other hand, Secondary sources comprise of various books, newspapers and magazines.

1.03 Objective of The Research

The main objectives of the paper are:

- A) An attempt has been made to show how the progressive consciousness is being reflected in the select poems of Hem Barua.
- b) Since Hem Barua was actively involved in socialism, this paper seeks to explore how his philosophy of life is being reflected in his poems.

2.00 Life and literary work of Hem Baruah.

Hem Barua was born on 1 April 1995 in Tezpur. He graduated from Tezpur Government High School in 1932 and Cotton College in 1936. He received his Masters degree in English Literature from the University of Calcutta in 1938. He started his career as an Assistant Professor in the Department of English from Jagannath Barua College, Jorhat. He was appointed Principal of Bholanath Barua College, Guwahati in 1944. He was also a leader in socialist politics. He was elected to the Lok Sabha from the Guwahati Parliamentary Constituency in the Second General Election in 1957 as a member of the Socialist Party. He was also elected from Guwahati and Mangaldai constituencies in the 1962 and 1967 general elections respectively. Hem Barua penned down both in English and Assamese literary world. He graced the chair of the President of Assam Sahitya Sabha in 1972 held in Dhubri.

The two collection of poems published by Hem Barua are – Balichanda(1959) and Mon Mayuri(1965). These two collections of poems and other unpublished poems were added later and republished under the title 'Hem Barua's Poems' (1985). His total number of poems is 67. While teaching in college, he translated the story “Kannaki Kalavan” into Assamese as ‘Kannaki’ (1960). He wrote several travelogue, including- Sagar Dekisha (1956), Ranga Karbir Phul (1958), Mekong Noi Dekilo (1967), and Izrail (1965). His other books include Modern Literature (1950), Qupid and Chyche (1959), Sanmihali (1957), Ei Gaon Ei Geet (1961), Sahitya

aru Sahitya (1962). Others books are- The August Revolution in Assam (1946), "The Red River and the Blue Hill" (1954), Fairs and Festivals of Assam (1956), Modern Assamese Poetry (1960), 'Assamese Literature' (1962), 'Folk Songs of India' (1965), "Lakshminath Bezbaruah" (1967), 'Idle Hours' (1961).

3.00 Progressive Thought in Hem Baruah's Poetry:

He was one of the most progressive poets in the world of modern Assamese poetry. He was a conscious public representative who understood the minds of the working Assamese people. Hem Baruah advocated the building of a progressive society. He wanted to abolish the capitalist society and build a healthy, classless society. Therefore, his poetry is characterized by progressive ideas.

Therefore, it is necessary to take into consideration the fact that the literary society of the present era should move forward on the path of creating a revolutionary new society. Hem Baruah urged poets and writers to keep pace with the times and himself spoke out against class discrimination in contemporary society. In the article, Sahitya Aaru Jugodharma, he says *If suffering could be eliminated so easily, there would be no need for Buddhas in religion, Marx and Angels in economics. Solving life's problems is not so easy. The problems of society can only be solved through society. Not by isolating yourself from society. This is especially needed in the era of class struggle. Being the forerunner of a society, there is a huge responsibility of poets for the upliftment of society.*²

The first collection of poems published by Hem Baruah, Balichanda, was influenced by communism. First, let us come to the discussion of the poem 'Upakantha', the second poem in the 'Balichanda'. The poet paints a realistic picture of the workers through the poem. The poem is an optimistic attitude towards the labor force

*“pathar upacha ghon boka aru pani
tate ami shramar kanikabur
eti etikoi eri jao*

shram hoi sonali dhanonir

amar sopun

tumar jonome jonome chinaki”- Upakantha

The poet tries to understand the suffering of the workers and dreams of building a new world through labour.

“aami jantar abiram goti hoi,

tez aru buku dhali,

haturire swapna saja

natun din aru natun prithivir.

haturer sabodat firingoti uthe

teekhar bukut aami likhu nava abhidhan” – (Upokantha)

The poet wants to advance the working force through the poem 'Upakantha' so that a classless society can be formed and economic equality can be established.

‘Puhoratkoi endhar val’ is the third poem in the collection of poems 'Balichanda' The poem is divided into seven stanzas. The poet wants to depict the terrible situation of World War II through the poem. During the war, humanism, love and beauty became irrelevant. The poet has lost his desire to live. ‘rajai-rajai’ in ‘ran-bigraht’.The condition of the common people is like that of ‘khandob dah agnisikha puri sai huwa birina fulor dae’.

The poem ends with an optimistic attitude, despite saying that ‘poharotkoi endhar val’, since Hem Barua was full of progressive thought.-

“sanka kihor

natun puwar kesa poharat aasar jui.

aamar sakut teekhar.”- ‘poharotkoi endhar val’

Another poem included in ‘Balichanda’, a collection of poems is ‘Prithivi’.The root cause of class inequality in society is the capitalist society. Therefore, the poet wishes for the end of the capitalist society and urges for the government of the people. This people are the exploited

and oppressed people. The poet is optimistic that the exploited and humiliated people will build a new society with new enterprises.-

*“ jibanok kune rudhib pare?
aami je patisu, aamar jibontholit
hezar kangsar mrityoushal.*

*hera cirajoubana, mor aadim prithivir
tomar mukhot sei cirparicitnhahi.*

*aamar lagote hahise aaji
janamanabar dal . aamar tez
utholi uthise tapot ban.” (prithivi)*

The poem expresses intense disgust, hatred and distrust towards the capitalist rulers and sympathy for exploited people is reflected in the poem ‘Aamar karone balichar aase’. Hatred and suspicion towards Capitalist rulers portrayed in this poem.

*“aamar kanthat ase piyah
Petor puroni, bukur jui.
Sakut swarnsabi
Poita vatat lon khorisa,
Poka jalokiya, var duporiyar juti.”- ‘Aamar karone balichar aase’.*

Another poem published in ‘Balichanda’ is ‘jaaror dinor sopun’. The poet depicts the conflict between the capitalist and working classes through the poem. The poet wishes for a stable society and the end of the capitalist (tejpiya) class.

*“mara prithivit tezar aaroti
eta tuni ahe , duta tuni ahe.
eta dhan niye, duta dhan niye.
dhanar domat tezpiyar ranachali
tezpiyar bangsha nasaloi kiman din baki?” (‘jaaror dinor sopun’)*

Another poem published in the Jayani Megazine is Puja. The poem 'Puja' expresses the hollow nature of capitalist, society. The poet is saddened by the plight of people belonging to the lower strata of the society. 'Puja' expresses class division of the society in a clear way.

*“eya puja satkora sha ana karubar puja
iman rong-rahoishya eya puja amar jodi hoi
kiy baru aaji ei maha anandar dina
aanandamoyee aagomoni khyanat
aami tahal disu klanta vagna
anahare suda pete
sau sihotar tarol bilash chai;
aajio amar pet udang
aajir dinao khudhar pet udang”.* (Puja)

The poem 'Eti Pook' by Hem Barua is a challenge to the capitalist society. Hem Barua wanted a revolutionary change in the capitalist society. He shows how class discrimination is prevalent in the society.

*“mor magojut ata pook
dhuwa anichita joon aru mekuri
sakur bismoy.
Eta pook
mor magojut ata pook
marubhumir trishatur swapna aru marcika
utt aru manuhar duta eta samodal
eta pook.”* - (eta pook)

4.00 Conclusion:

To conclude, it can be said that, Hem Barua's poems is a realistic portrayal of issues related to society. Through his poems, he wanted to inject progressive ideas upon the minds of the readers. He dreamt of shaping a world wherein there would be no division in terms of class and caste.

Reference Notes:

1. Huzuri, Samindra: Natun Sahitya, p 14
2. Barua, Hem: Adhunik Sahitya, p 4-5

Bibliography-

1. Katki, Chandra : *Aadhunik Asomiya Kobita*, Second Edition, Guwahati: Chandra Prakash,1989
- 2 Kalita, Maheshwar : *Challichar Dashakar Asamiya Kabita : Eti Samiksha*, First Edition, Guwahati: Jyoti Prakashan, 2002
3. Bargohain, Homen: *Esha Basarar Asomiya Kabita*, Fourth Edition, Guwahati Assam Prakashan Parishad, 2008
4. Barua, Hem : *Adhunik Sahitya*, First Edition, Guwahati: Sankardev Library,1950
5. --- : *Hem Baruar Kabita*, First Edition, Guwahati LBS, Publications,1986
6. Bhattacharya,Purna :*Adhunik Asomiya Kabita*, First Edition, Guwahati: Chandra Prakash,2001
7. Hujubi, Samindra: *Natun Sahitya*, 22nd Issue, Guwahati Natun Sahitya Parishad,2014